

Review

Understand The Factors Affect Student's Academic Performance in Science Subjects in Public Secondary Schools in Tanzania

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Abstract: *This study reports the findings on Understand the factors affect student's academic performance in science subjects in public secondary schools in Tanzania, by drawing references from public secondary schools found at Dodoma Municipal in Tanzania. To achieve this end, the following specific objectives were formulated such as: To examine the availability of teaching and learning materials for science subjects in secondary schools, to identify the pass rate and drop rates in science subjects, to highlight the difficulties or challenges faced by teachers and students in learning science subjects in secondary schools. 30 respondents were selected and data were collected through interviews, observation and documentary review. The analysis of the data revealed that there is congestion of students in class, shortage of laboratories as well as chemicals for practical, lack of enough and quality text books. Furthermore analysis revealed that, teaching and learning of science subjects affected by students and teachers perception, shortage of qualified competent teachers in teaching science subjects. Following the findings researcher suggested that teaching and learning resources in science subjects like books, laboratory apparatus have to be increased to schools to enable students to interact effectively through discussion and other participatory strategies associated in order to improve performance in science subjects. In addition to that, the existence of many students in a single stream affect the teaching and learning process. The government under the ministry of education and vocational training, NGOs and other*

educational stake holders should have public awareness on the significance of studying science subjects for the current and future development of Tanzania. Those education players should put more emphasize on science subjects and the ministry of education should ensure that all public secondary schools have all resources for teaching and learning.

Keywords: *Factors, Academic, Performance, Science Subjects*

1. Introduction

Tanzania education system follows 2-7-4-2-3+- - - whereby 2 years of pre-primary school and then comes 7 years of primary school. The secondary education is split into ordinary and advanced level of secondary education. As for tertiary education, there are four and two years of education respectively for each level of certificate or diploma awarded: Certificate of Secondary Education Examination (CSEE) and certificate or diploma awarded: Advanced Certificate of Secondary Education Examination (ACSEE). After which students are expected to join with the various tertiary education institutions for specialization in various professionals. However the education system in Tanzania is now in the process of being restructured to offer 11 years of free compulsory basic education. This will moves to 1-6-4-2-3+- - - structure. However, this is yet to be accommodated in the new education act which will enshrine it into Tanzanian law. The main differences from the previous 13 structure are that both one year of pre-primary and four years of lower secondary are now free and compulsory.

The Education and Training Policy of 1995 insist on the need to promote science and technology education in schools to meet future science and technology goals in the dynamic world. In secondary schools, there have been a shortage of qualified science teachers which pushed the government to train Form Six leavers for few months in order to try to cover this gap. Since 1990s, the united republic of Tanzania in collaboration with different international organization such as GTZ, whereby established different strategies to arrest the appalling quality of education including the in-service teachers education and training of resource in 1997. According to Osaki (2007), although all those initiatives taken by the government of Tanzania to overcome the massive failure of students in science subjects, the situation has remained hectic year after year. Currently, in many public secondary schools in Tanzania students read teacher's notes instead of reading text books while teacher centered approach is the common methodology used in teaching students. These

notes often encourage rote learning in order to pass tests and other examinations in school (Kalolo, 2015).

Teaching and learning in science subjects place a lot of difficulties to teachers and is setting an alarm to stake holders in education, government, parents and schools. Currently, many countries are experiencing a gradual dropdown on student's participation and performance in science subjects (Msoka, Mtebe, Kissaka, & Kalinga, 2015). Apart from that, the failure in science subjects raises some doubts and debate on how teachers teach and how students learn. Some see that the failure in these subjects as a result of the teachers due to lack of important teaching competencies while others see the failure as a result from lack of students motivation in science subjects (Kafyulilo, 2010).

1.2 Statement of the problem

Science knowledge act as a gear for the development of any country important in under this century of globalization. This knowledge is mostly required in the developing countries whose industrial development is a panacea to the economic hindrances. In a precise definition, science is required to develop machineries, infrastructures, and processing some goods. It goes without saying that science takes a large package of the strategies towards development. While the fore assertions remain true, the performance in science subjects in public secondary schools in Tanzania has remained a big problem since independence. There have been some efforts in place to arrest this situation but the problem still persist. For example, there had been a program to improve the performance and shape science subjects' curriculum through Teacher Education in Mathematics and Science (TEAMS) under the University of Dar es Salaam also the support in service teacher education. The emphasize is that teaching and learning of science subjects need urgent and effective remedies, example of the remedies includes teacher support materials and provision of the relevant resources in all secondary schools to improve teaching and learning science subjects. However, there is no empirical evidence which are available to inform the factors affect students' academic performance in science subjects in secondary schools in Tanzania of where there has been abundant support to rescue the situation. Any relevant remedy or intervention needs to be informed by research and this current study is in that direction to inform of the reasons. Dodoma municipal taken as a reference of the study.

1.3 Objectives of the study

- i. To examine the availability of teaching and learning materials for science subjects in secondary schools.
- ii. To identify the pass rate and drop rates in science subjects.
- iii. To highlight the difficulties or challenges faced by teachers and students in learning science subjects in secondary schools.

2. The context of teaching and learning of science subjects

Quality basic science education does not exist in isolation way in schools. Outside school there are many contexts where students can meet and learn about science through the media like Television, films, newspapers, internet and so on. Increasing interest in science careers is not simply a challenge by providing resources for schools, frequently subsidizing materials or making them available on the internet (Moeed, 2013). In many countries, the numbers of scientists is relatively small and they already have a great wide range of demands placed upon them, so it needed to ensure that they are used effectively.

Individual teachers or schools can make significant progress in their particular contexts. When it comes to the wider development, the case for all stake holders acting together is clear. Different sorts of expertise are needed to transform these connections into the ways would help students to learn because teachers, scientists and science educators have power and also influence deep changes in students science learning (Barnes, 2008). Sorts of expertise are needed to transform these connections into the ways would help students to learn because teachers, scientists and science educators have power and have deep changes in students science learning. Science lessons can take on several forms, they include the practical lesson, the demonstration lesson, the theoretical lesson, supported by well-defined activities and the problem solving lesson. For optimum learner performance, the academic year of a learner should comprise of all the above type of lessons.

This would allow learners to take hands on approach to their learning and process as well as think critically and creatively through the process of stimulation and communication with other learners by building their existing knowledge through the process of constructivism. According to Ingersoll & Perda (2009) there is a shortage of qualified science educators and this is expected to worsen the situation over the years as very few students are taking up careers in science teaching. When there is inadequate preparation on the part of teacher and a limited academic background, the result is poor teaching in school. Different research shows that although educators can sometimes master

the theory of physical sciences, putting the theory into practice is a major problem. The pedagogical knowledge that teachers gain through their qualifications must be applied to the teaching of science, thereby narrowing the gap between theory and practice.

Scientific language has specific demands; there is an extensive vocabulary to learn. Some studies show that the vocabulary demands of some secondary school science programs are greater than those of second language programs (Carrier, 2012). This is clearly expecting too much, particularly if the language of instruction is not the same as the student's home language. There have been many reports on how science uses. This vocabulary in tends to be different from everyday language use.

The emphasis is on the basic science education, on understanding rather than simple reproduction of information. This means that students should use the language in which they feel most comfortable, especially when they meet new ideas. They should be developing, understanding first and technical vocabulary to be the second. The language challenges vary within and between countries. In some countries, like Bolivia where there are several official languages, teachers are expected to be at least bi – lingual. Such language skills mean that early or basic science education can be in a language that reflects the local community; however, this solution does not solve the many, often delicate issues of language diversity and their connections with social class and ethnicity (Halliday, M.A.K & Webster, 2004).

In rich countries, there are enough teachers to meet the requirements of a teacher to all students, though in less developed countries (LDCs) teachers are often motivated by a sense of service and prestige. Teaching and learning become difficult where there is a lack of infrastructure, as such equipment and laboratories for later stages of schooling, inadequate salaries and career structure, teacher motivation and retention drops (Umar, Adamu, & Sadiq, 2014). Teachers to teach science subjects is more strongly associated with science performance and students expectation of working in a science related occupation than the material and human resources of science departments, including the qualifications of teachers or the kinds of extracurricular in science activities offered to students. For instance in almost all education systems, students score high in science subjects when their science teachers explain scientific ideas, discuss their questions or demonstrate an idea more frequently (PISA, 2015).

In most participating countries and economies, the socio- economic status and an immigrant background are related with significant differences in students' performance. For example,

disadvantaged students score 88 which is points lower in science than the advantaged students, on average across OECD countries and in more than 40 countries and economies and after accounting for students' academic performance in the science assessment, disadvantaged students remain significantly less likely than their advantaged peers to see themselves pursuing a career in science.

To enhance learning in science subjects, teachers need to have a focus on the relationship that exists between the educational tasks. The majority of teachers and schools pay more attention on pedagogy and content forgetting the technological domain. Science and Mathematics subjects are currently placing a lot of challenges to teachers on how they teach to students and on how they learn. The increasing failures in these subjects have become a concern for all stake holders in education: government, parents, curriculum developers and schools (Blatchford, Russell & Bassett, 2007).

2.1 State of teaching and learning science subjects in secondary schools in Tanzania

Tanzanian secondary schools students and teachers obviously continue to interact with indigenous and curricular – based on natural science knowledge but rarely teachers attempt to render tough materials relevant to everyday life. In recent years, the situation in secondary schools with regard to the basic or core teaching and learning resources including the number of classrooms, furniture, laboratories, science equipment, chemicals, text books, up to date syllabus for various subjects and staff housing were either un available and a cutely in sufficient, shortages are further exacerbated as a result of HIV pandemic that has seriously impacted the teaching profession (Semali & Mehta, 2012).

A majority of students participate in science subjects, especially Physics, Chemistry, as well as Biology and Mathematics at their secondary education level do fail, while the country is in great demand of experts like engineers, doctors, accountants, science and mathematical teachers as well as agricultural officers (Kitta, 2004). The Government of Tanzania has set high goals to become middle – income country by 2025 (Planning Commission, 2014). This is perceived as a devastating finding in that science and technology is considered as the driving force to reach this goal. As a result of a lack of science teachers and low quality in science teaching presents major problems for Tanzanian's schools.

Some public secondary schools do not have even a single science teacher, some schools recruit part – time science teachers, especially form 6 (high school graduates, Dodoma, District

Education officer, 2014). The lack of facilities contributes to the failing to teach and learn science. According to the national policy, every secondary school should have three laboratories one each for Physics, Chemistry and Biology. However, only a few schools had all three laboratories, and only few public schools and private schools owned by Christian based organizations had at least a laboratory and a library. There were no public community schools has any laboratories and libraries (HakiElimu, 2014).

As cited in Birgen (2005), asserted that experience and qualification is the best assessment or handling a tasks. In his findings, teaching is one of the duties that require both qualification and experience for the better delivery. Recruitment of competent teachers to improve teacher – student ratio is necessary to measure performance of students. For instance, the Government of Tanzania should give adequate attention to training of teachers to enhance good performance of students in Mathematics (Yara & Omondi, 2010).

The low – quality of text books and the multiple sets of text books cause a lot of confusion and chaos for teachers, create students’ performance subjects to be a problem in a national examinations. There are many mistakes in the text books, leading both teachers and students to be wrongly informed. Teachers complained bitterly of having received no training on the syllabus and that some text books have incorrect information and others have very little content to cover a whole period of class (Kitta, 2004), explored a number of factors that consistently affect to a large extent the performance in science subjects among ordinary level secondary school students in Tanzania. These were such as schools being occupied by unqualified and under qualified teachers that had problems with pedagogical content knowledge and teaching skills.

3. Materials and methods

The study was conducted at Dodoma municipal and involved three schools which were randomly sampled. The study employed qualitative approach. The sample of the study included 30 respondents from three secondary schools, whereby from those three secondary schools 10 respondents were interviewed including 5 students, 4 science teachers and 1 head of school in each school so as to get different views concerning to the problem. In this study qualitative data were obtained through interviews, observation and documentary review and later analyzed through thematic or content analysis. The sample size and category of respondents is depicted in the table below.

Table 1: Participants of the study

Institutions	Students	Teachers	Head of schools	Total
School A	05	04	01	10
School B	05	04	01	10
School C	05	04	01	10
Total	15	12	03	30

Source: Field Data

In this study qualitative data were obtained through interviews, observation and documentary review later on analyzed through thematic or content analysis. Thematic or content involves reduction and sense- making effort that takes a volume of qualitative material and attempts to identify core consistencies and meaning.

4. Results and Discussion

The availability of teaching and learning materials in science subjects

Availability of teaching and learning materials in science subjects in the three sampled schools was obtained through interview and observation. The findings in general indicated that some basic teaching and learning materials in science subjects such as; books and availability of laboratories and practical teaching.

The availability of books in the three sampled schools

The science subjects that were taught at the three sampled schools were Biology, Physics as well as Chemistry. From the three sampled schools, there were two different books for each of the subject for example Biology, Chemistry and Physics. Each subject had a text book and a reference book. The text books were found not enough to meet the available number of students in class. All 12 teachers and three heads of schools, as well as students, all affirmed that the books were not enough to meet the number of the students. They all admitted that the book student ratio was not good, it means the number of text book did not correlate with the number of enrolled students in science subjects from school A, B and C.

Table 2: Existing Science Books in Secondary Schools and its Deficit

School	No of students	No of subjects	Existing Books	Required Books	Deficit	Ratio of BK/ST
A	580	Maths	140	580	440	1:4
		Biology	120	580	460	1:5
		Chemistry	50	320	270	1:1
		Physics	62	272	210	1:9
B	598	Maths	100	598	498	1:6
		Biology	110	598	488	1:6
		Chemistry	99	420	321	1:6
		Physics	75	383	308	1:7
C	629	Maths	100	629	529	1:6
		Biology	80	629	549	1:8
		Chemistry	102	480	378	1:6
		Physics	98	398	300	1:6

Source: Field Data

The study revealed that the number of books, especially textbooks were not correlate with the number of students found in the three sampled schools. This problem seems to be persistent since the same had been observed to be affecting students since 2015. For example (Kapinga, 2017) reported that the number of books available in public secondary schools in Tanzania do not meet the number of students found within a school.

On the same opinion, another head of school from school B reported that:

“The available resources like science books are not enough for the students available. At our school, one book is used by almost 6 students. This is because the books are few compared to students available” (Head Teacher from school “B” 27th August 2018).

Availability of laboratories and chemicals for practical teaching

The first research objective assessed the availability of teaching and learning materials or facilities. The findings of the three sampled schools revealed that there was no science laboratories in all schools visited. Each school had a single room whereby all the apparatus and chemicals for all the three subjects that is Biology, Chemistry as well as Physics were found within a single room. In school B they had no even a room to store laboratory equipment for were kept in the shelves in a store room. The purpose was to establish whether or not laboratories were effectively used in schools to make practices contribute to poor academic performance in science subjects. Findings of this study revealed that only school A could make some practices with very few apparatus. In schools findings show that practical are conducted only during examination times. One of the interviewed students elaborated this problem with an argument that:

“It is not that we are taught with practical in science subjects.

We normally learn theoretically in Form One to Form Three. We are taught in practical when it is reach form four near the national examination time.”

(Interview, 30th August 2018, SCHOOL B).

Mulela (2015), cemented the above findings with the argument that, practical teaching promotes the development of cognitive abilities such as problem-solving, analysis, generalizing, evaluating, decision making and creativity to perform well in examinations. Additionally, the above findings were supported by the head of school C, who had this to say: *“Our students do not conduct practical regularly. This is because we run short of chemicals and other facilities. Therefore, we only buy some chemicals when the Form Four national examinations approach. The chemicals that remain during normal practical are used for some of the practical in the lower classes.”* **(Head of school “C” 31st August 2018, SCHOOL C).**

Putting these findings together, it can be argued that, students from the sampled public schools do not perform well in science because they do not make enough practical when learning.

To identify the pass rate and drop rates in science subjects

In order to respond the second objective, this study used documentary review to see the academic performance of students in Form Four national examination results in Biology, Chemistry and Physics from 2015 – 2017 years.

Table 3: Performance of students in CSEE 2015 – 2017 for science subjects

Name of School	Year	Biology Grades						Chemistry Grades						Physics Grades					
		A	B	C	D	F	Tot	A	B	C	D	F	Tot	A	B	C	D	F	Tot
SA	2015	1	2	15	28	96	142	1	2	5	13	85	106	0	0	6	16	8	30
	2016	4	5	19	53	70	151	0	2	9	19	81	111	0	0	6	11	9	26
	2017	1	3	21	39	48	112	1	0	13	19	15	48	0	0	4	15	2	21
SB	2015	0	0	3	15	53	71	0	0	2	4	26	32	0	0	1	5	2	8
	2016	0	0	2	19	53	74	0	0	2	5	18	25	0	0	1	4	1	6
	2017	0	0	10	11	39	60	0	0	2	12	6	20	0	0	3	5	1	9
SC	2015	0	4	13	27	106	150	0	0	11	13	7	31	0	0	4	9	1	14
	2016	0	2	11	17	131	162	0	1	6	6	15	28	0	1	1	5	1	8
	2017	0	0	6	12	65	83	1	0	3	5	28	37	0	0	2	6	2	10

Source: National Examination Council of Tanzania (2015 - 2017)

The table above indicates that out of 363 candidates of the three sampled schools who sat for the Biology exam in the year 2015, only 108 passed at the A to D grades. The rest scored grade F which means they failed the examination. In 2016, out of 287, only 132 scored grade A to D.

The performance in science subjects in SB in the year 2015, shows that no candidate obtained Grade A and B in Biology, no candidate obtained grade A, B in Chemistry and Physics. In SC no candidate obtained grade A in all science subjects while in SA no candidate scored grade A in Physics subject.

This implies that the three sampled schools were not performing well in Tanzania national results. For example, a reported from (HakiElimu, 2014) that despite the strategies conducted to increase the academic performance in science subjects but still the performance of Physics and Chemistry subjects has not gone beyond 50% of the students that sit for examination. This was also reported by Limbe (2017) that from 2010 to 2016 students Physics subject were less than 50% of all students who sat for that examination.

To highlight the difficulties or challenges faced by teachers and students in learning science subjects in secondary schools

Many secondary schools in Tanzania especially the public one face several challenges, during the whole process of teaching and learning. At the end of the day students perform poorly in national examination. To respond the third objective the researcher identified number of students per class and adequate number of science teachers as the main challenges in teaching and learning science subjects.

Table 4: Average number of students per each class

School	Form 1			Form 2			Form 3			Form 4			Average
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	
SA	50	51	48	56	58	52	47	49	43	50	46	48	50
SB	63	59	Nil	59	57	Nil	48	47	Nil	46	48	Nil	53
SC	49	52	47	52	48	49	52	48	53	51	48	60	51

Source: Field Data 2018

The three sampled public secondary schools in Dodoma City, the average class size was high than the recommended number of students. The recommended number of students 40 students for secondary schools and 45 for primary school. This is recommended by the Education and Training Policy (1995) that in Tanzania, the average class size in secondary school is 40 students and 45 pupils in primary education. Furthermore, the class size available is against the Current Education Policy available. However, the study of the same nature was conducted in Karagwe district by (Kanyamwenge, 2017), and found that the average class size was high than the recommended size, the class size was observed to be for 82 students. Similarly, these findings concur with those studies by UNESCO (2005) which revealed that the class size is high in developing countries when compared to developed countries like USA, Japan, China and others, in Sub Saharan Africa. There are more problems experienced in countries like Malawi and Zambia which are revealed to have the class size between 73 and 88 students. Other studies have come up with similar arguments as those put forth by Pedder (2006) who revealed that there the class size is large in developing countries than in developed ones. This was also reported by one of the head of school who argued that:

“The class area is small compared to the number of students available at my school, many students sit on one desk, because

we don't have any alternative. We cannot even make them attend school in shifts because we don't have enough teachers to teach in two sessions a day. This makes the classrooms very congested. In these streams, we find that we have 60 to 63 students per each stream.” (Head of school “A” 27th August 2018, SCHOOL A).

This was found to increase difficulties for teachers to access all students during teaching process.

The findings of this study concur with the statement by Blatchford (2009) that larger classes often result in the wasting of instructional time and less academic performance. The implication is that large classes require teachers to spend more time outside of the classroom for the completion of non-instructional tasks which leads to teacher dissatisfaction and tiredness. On the same view a teacher from school B had this to say;

“Unavailability of enough classrooms and budget fund to build enough classes has resulted in a great number of students sitting in single class this is not a new thing because not public school in this City has less than 60 students in a single stream. Those are streams you find stream A has 60 the other more than that, although there are enough desks in secondary schools there are no classrooms to put them”. (A teacher from school B, 27th August, 2018).

With these findings, it is clear that the sitting arrangement poses some difficulties for the students to learn well and participate fully in class, especially when teaching science subjects that need much attention and need more cooperative learning methods more than arts subjects.

The findings of this study show that a large number of teachers, for example more than half of the teachers mentioned that class environment is not conducive to allow class interaction during teaching and learning of science subjects. The implication is that it becomes difficult for teachers to deliver and manage the class because of the number of students available in class thus, this results in poor academic performance. These results are in hand to hand with the findings of the study done by Saga (2014) who reported that large classes often result in teachers using

much time in instructing students but because of large number this result into less academic achievement.

Table 5: Number of science teachers

School	Physics	Chemistry	Biology
	Number of Teachers	Number of Teachers	Number of Teachers
SA	2	1	3
SB	1	2	2
SC	1	1	2

Source: Field Data 2018

From all sampled schools, no any school in any given subjects had more than 3 teachers. There were some teachers who supposed to teach other subjects despite of not majoring them in colleges. They were to assist in teaching those subjects provided that they had pursued a science combination. For example if a teacher had studied PCB meaning Physics, Chemistry and Biology at A level and specialized in only Chemistry at college was supposed to assist teaching other science subjects like Physics and Biology in those schools due to shortage of those teachers.

Lyimo (2017) holds the same view that, most secondary schools in Tanzania face shortage of science teachers. It was further explained that most of science teachers were found to be more overloaded with teaching load that made them not teach at the load needed. The government was encouraged to employ more science teachers in public secondary schools so as to increase the number and rate of science subjects performance among students.

5. General factors affect student’s academic performance in science subjects in secondary schools

Absenteeism of science teachers

Twaweza (2016) reported that most teachers in Tanzania are not regularly attending at school, due to insufficient amount of salary which does not satisfy their daily life. Due to this, teachers decide to engage in individual activities during school hour. The findings reported that some of the students said that teachers do not attend classes as allocated on the time table and this leads

the students to reach the national examination before completion of the needed topic. Therefore absenteeism of teachers affect the students' performance.

Poor perception among students

In most of the public community secondary schools some students believe incapable of studying science subjects due to discouragement from their teachers. In Tanzania the huge number of students believe that science subjects are difficult. From this study one of the science teacher reported that students believe science subjects are tough it become difficult for them to study those subjects especially Biology subject which is the compulsory subject to all students.

Lack of motivation to teachers and students

More ever (Akani, 2016) reported that science subjects are difficult subjects, so motivation is needed to both teachers and students, in order to attract teaching and learning process to ensure maximum academic achievement in science subjects to the learners in public community secondary. The findings reported that one science teacher said that the issue of motivation is a problem in their school, because the school is not providing any kind of motivation to teachers or students. In academic issues motivation is very important because it help a lot for a learner to study but most of public schools do not do like that.

Lack of sufficient subject content knowledge and qualified teachers

The occurrence of this problem has accelerated the decrease in students' pass rate of science subjects in national examination to the large extent in secondary schools. According to World Bank (2019)reported that more than 10,400 science teachers in secondary schools in Tanzania absolutely do not have, and at the same time do not know the sufficient subject content knowledge of the subjects they teach. For example science and mathematics account for 46% of the curriculum while 28% of teachers are qualified to teach science subjects. The findings from this study revealed that no any secondary school in any given subjects had more than 3 teachers, teachers were used to teach other subjects despite of not majoring them in colleges. Therefore, at the end of the day lack of sufficient subject content knowledge from teachers affect students' performance in science subjects in secondary schools within Tanzania.

Presence of Job Dissatisfaction among Teachers

Different studies indicate that in many secondary schools most of the teachers in secondary school suffer with job and career dissatisfaction something which affects students' achievement in science subjects. Due to lower self-efficacy and characterized by high level of anxiety, so these kinds of teachers tend to ruin the achievement of students toward science subjects (Njiru, 2014). Apart from that the research findings revealed that teachers from those targeted schools tend to develop negative attitude to the learners and their interaction to students is negatively.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained, the study provides the following conclusion to reflect the specific objectives about this study. First, the study found that, all schools had no enough books. The ration was found that six students per one book. Laboratories were not enough only single room was used as laboratory room to all three subjects. Apart from that findings indicated that the pass rate and drop rate in science subjects in all three sampled schools were not performing well in Tanzania national examination results. Despite of the strategies employed to increase the academic performance in science subjects but still the performance of Physics and Chemistry subjects has not gone beyond 50% of the students that sat for national examination. With respect to the third objective concerning about challenges face both teachers and students in teaching and learning science subjects, the study concludes that number of students found in class was another challenge in teaching science subjects using experiments while number of students is high. Finally, other challenges faced by students include few teachers and most teachers are incompetence in teaching science subjects.

Recommendations for actions

Teaching and learning resources in science subjects like books, laboratory apparatus have to be increased to schools to enable students to interact effectively through discussion and other participatory strategies associated in order to improve performance in science subjects. Furthermore, the existence of many students in a single stream affect the teaching and learning process. Thus, some students fail to follow what the teacher is teaching. Apart from that sometimes it is difficult for teachers to give home work to students because of the scarcity of teaching and learning materials.

The government under the ministry of education and vocational training, NGOs and other educational stake holders should have public awareness on the significance of studying science subjects for the current and future development of Tanzania. Those education players should put more emphasize on science subjects and the ministry of education should ensure that all public secondary schools have all resources for teaching and learning. More ever school inspector officers should fulfill their responsibility by visiting schools in order to see how the teaching and learning process takes place.

Science teachers need to be innovative in order to modify their teaching methods at the same time to embrace the benefits of interactive teaching during learning process. Actually science teachers need to use different methods during the teaching process so as to attract the students at the same time that method should suit the needs of the students. For example Teachers should eliminate the use of lecture method during teaching instead they are supposed to increase the use of learner centered approach something which will increase the development of skills and increase the performance in Tanzania.

Recommendations for further studies

The current study was limited to one Urban district that is Dodoma Municipal at Dodoma City. It is therefore recommended that other studies covering a wider part of Tanzania be done in order to provide the understanding on the factors contributing to poor performance in science subjects among public secondary schools.

The current study was limited in public secondary schools. It is therefore recommended to have research conducted in private secondary schools and compare with public schools to find out how students perform in these subjects.

The samples used in the current study were students, teachers and head teachers discovered to narrow information. Therefore the study recommends further researches to be done that will include various participants from different government organizations such as policymakers, administrative, parents and community who always observe poor performance in science subjects among their children.

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Dedication

I dedicate this article to all teachers, researchers as well as students in my country to read.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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